

Axioms of Influence, Affluence, and Access

Influence comes from Access, and Affluence from Influence. Therefore there is a *flux* and a *currency* that must generate leverage in these three regions or spheres of affect (on power). These are related to the axioms of power, especially social, political, and monetary, and are therefore affected also by the axioms of power, particularly actual power, martial, political, and even sexual power.

Nevertheless, there must be some concrete rules which do not only depend on charm, personality, and luck. Those axioms will also be mentioned. The author does not come from influence, affluence, or access (although he had government access at one point, but within that structure had no more access or aid) and has had to 'crack in' his entire life. But what he has learned, in increasing his affluence and influence from basically nothing - almost an afterthought or forgotten and abandoned being at birth and a young age - he will now share, whether it be cynical, realistic, optimistic, or even pessimistic/negative.

Rules of Access	Rules of Influence	Rules of Affluence
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Access is given, it is not taken ➤ Access is easily lost ➤ Access is ironically inaccessible to most ➤ Access comes from Affluence ➤ Access nourishes Influence ➤ Access is a lock and key; it requires the right lock and key to open doors ➤ Access is cold, simple, wirey, and immutable; it requires discretion and control. ➤ Access can never be excess ➤ Access can be tracked, quantified, described, cataloged, etc. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Influence is not pressure, it is a friendly or collegial nudge. ❖ Influence can be bought, gained, lost, transferred, expanded, shrunk, or stolen. ❖ Influence, to some degree, depends upon mutual adoration ❖ Influence flows, especially along power vectors. ❖ Where power vectors clash or are working at cross purposes, influence is essential to determining the Shi ❖ Influence is the heart of Affluence (central to the mechanics of it). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ★ Affluence extends from influence, but includes monetary position. ★ Affluence nurtures Access ★ Affluence has a ripening schedule; and it can rot things ★ Affluence matures, usually with the person or family ★ Family affluence is powerful, for either good or evil ★ Affluence influences envy. ★ Affluence yields fruits, and these have consequences. ★ Affluence is no guarantee of influence or Access, but it is not a moot factor either.

A: The Degrees of Access¹

1. In the beginning, Access is cold, and things can be said to be *inaccessible*.
 - a. It is typical that parents and their own access and network provides the first roots of access.
 - b. Also in Asia, young boys are encouraged to find a master/mentor to gain early Access; of course there is a risk of sexual assault, and this has been a problem since the beginnings of such practices. For example Alexander the Great may have been a sexual pupil of Aristotle. But there is no doubt that Alexander benefited from the gathering of Access that Socrates > Plato > Aristotle could provide, and this led to his successes.

¹ Literally temperatures

2. From the beginning, it is desirable to build a child or young adult's network, and increase their Access, and this will be aided by *warm feelings* from sympathetic persons.
3. Access heats up with not mere warmth, but the combination or *compounding* of factors, such as charm, provision of mutual value, addition to one another's mutual credibility or reputation, etc.
4. Access temperature increases degrees by degrees, but it cannot merely *melt the lock*, the heat has to warm up a relationship, or situation, until the heat - at the **right temperature** - unlocks the keybox.
5. The keybox is the storage of potential for Access; for example, it could be a promised license, degree, or certificate, withheld by an authority until the situation has satisfied a greater power structure.
 - a. The Access is first given to enter the path to the keybox then the keybox is opened when the conditions are satisfied, then the key is presented, and finally the doors to the world desired are unlockable, so long as the door is within reach, and the key fits.
6. If the heat is excessive - greed or overlust, forcefulness in relationships (which oft give power over oneself rather than *to oneself*) - then the keybox is destroyed, or removed (perhaps the Access is what is destroyed).
7. If one has not exceeded propriety, however, the keybox is not destroyed, rather one must simply *not give up*.²
8. The fires of impropriety can burn the keybox in a flash.
9. Degree by degree, the goal to Access is reached by warmth and **warming the hearts of others**.
10. If one is cold by nature, this will take a lot of practice, or psychotic lying. If one is hot then cold, time the self with the Changes and nature's seasons and the weather, so that one is hot when it is cold, and cool when there is heat, etc.

B: The Lock and Door

1. Once one has the key which is desired, it is important to match the key to the door and use the door.
2. To do this, consider the lock. There are many lock types.
3. Official locks require officially approved keys; there is no quick or fake substitute, or you will be discovered, discredited, and lose everything.
4. Backdoor locks take many forms of fake and real keys; so for example many use faked credentials, money, 'wink and a nod', sex, mere handshakes and promises, speculation, and faked reports or documents.
5. Other locks are custom, and require the finding of custom keys; which usually requires the legwork to meet the right person, or to know the person who knows the person who knows the Way to the key to success.
6. Therefore the heat must be spread to raise the temperature widely; and never underestimate the value of any person.
7. It is better to have the heat of hate than a cold frigid heart.
8. But it is a sad thing when the fire of hate destroys unknown key boxes through hasty words and decisions; and Access which could have been found or created, is never manifested.
9. Therefore the words of Confucius or Buddha about forethought before speaking, comes to mind.

² There are many stories of people who worked their whole lives to crack into world and heights of power and affluence, despite all odds. There are also, conversely, plenty of stories of powerful people who lost all power, access, and affluence, despite all their influence, because of impropriety. Most recently Jeffrey Epstein and Harvey Weinstein come to mind. Epstein was then destroyed himself by the very powers that gave Access and Affluence, so even he was destroyed with the keybox!

10. When one is presented with both a key and a lock one must decide whether or not to 'look a gift horse in the mouth'; bear in mind that doing so may likely reveal evil or manipulative intentions, and yet otherwise may be exactly what one needs. It all depends on the control of Position.

C: The Keys to Access

1. The type of key will depend upon the type of door.
2. If the door is shady, do not expect a clean, golden key; if the door is bright and promising, do not expect to use a shady key. Match key for door, because the lock will not allow cross typing.
3. Picking locks without key does not guarantee Access, and likely it'll simply be taken away.
4. Brief Access only works for crimes.
5. Long term Access takes a lot of work, and so it will be advisable to find the keyboxes which lead to unlocking the shiniest keys. These keyboxes will all increase the degrees of Access, but not necessarily with mere heat. It may shine the keys, sharpen them, make them more weighty (adding to one's gravitas), etc.
6. Big keys come from big people.
7. Little keys come from big and little people; but they are not of equal quality or ability.
8. Do not discount the value of little keys as they may be free keybox openings for the larger key boxes which lead to the right locks.
9. But it may also be that any freely given key has strings; it is likely that the giver wants Access or Influence.
10. A key can be broken *in the lock*, even the correct lock (perhaps especially the right one, leaving it inaccessible); therefore, deft handling of the key in the lock is necessary to remain able to use the door.

D: The Door to Influence

1. A door rests upon hinges, therefore the turning of people means pushing and pulling.
2. Doors are of various quality, density/solidity, security, promise/opportunity, inertia, strength or weakness, and lifespan of use.
3. A door which leads directly to influence may happen upon one *unplanned*, so **expect the unexpected**.
4. Doors of influence of a person are also called gaps or cracks, and the rules for the motion or use of these are covered best in the Guiguzi, or the rhetors/sophists of Greece.
5. Doors of influence of a company, organization, group, etc. tend to remain in the power of networks, and of given Access, but *definitely* will be guarded by and related to (symbiotic with) Affluence.
6. Some people have natural presence, umph, charm, 'it', and they will have the door to Influence easily opened. Don't complain about this, try to absorb or saddle up next to them. This 'heat' is spiritual.
7. Once a doorway to Influence has been opened: *prop it open*, or secure it, or if it is a special, unique door, hide its secrets by closing the door and speaking little of it.
8. If the room behind the door is mostly empty, or needs more people, announce the existence of the door, and invite in the affluent, who have Access, and require their keys, to enter.
9. Once a door is secured, or guarded, check on it.
10. If a door is too heavy, or dense, it is good for security but can break the hinges, and become useless; if a door is too light it will not be believable or securable, and the contents of the room will be stolen easily. Access will be lost. Affluence will leak away as the influence wanes.

E: Purchasing Influence

1. There are people who make their living busting down doors with money, and if enough doors open, Influence leads to more money and more doors and it snowballs into true Influence and Affluence.
2. This shiney *golden key* is recognizable to the select, elite and it is measured in the size, quality, and opportunities it can unlock.
3. They say it cannot be bought, and is a matter of character, quality, honor, breeding, etc. but in the end it is just about the Value proposition - the money.
4. Influence of this kind is like wind over various objects; more wind means more influence, but some objects bend and some defy the power of the wind, causing it to go around.
5. This wind flows along the gradients of Positional Advantage (shi), and goes along with it.
6. Therefore the wind currents and the monetary currency are directly proportional; at some point more currency will not guarantee more Influence.
7. This will frustrate the affluent who have bought Influence but not Access. It will confuse them. They may lash out in anger; hate may flow in all sorts of misdirections and destroy key boxes.
8. When a door appears like a wall, the lock has not been found, or cannot be picked; it means that there is a key not found; it may mean that Influence must be purchased for a treasure hunter to find the keybox.
9. Professional hunters of keys may include consultants, lawyers, bankers, etc. The main thing is that this purchase of Influence holds no guarantees, but it will almost certainly gain new types of Access.
10. Misdirected wind, and resultant Access, may be a purposeful misdirection, and so pay attention to the degrees of Access, and to whom the keys serve, and what types of baubles are behind the doors the keys open.

F: Insuring Influence

1. Insurance is not assurance; it costs money. Assurances are essentially worthless.
2. Insurance premiums are variable, and also they are not of equivalent value; but in the case of Influence Insurance, few will limit their expenditures.
3. Mostly Influence is insured by a guarantee of continued cashflow.
4. This means risk assessment, investigation, and analysis. It doesn't pay to be lazy.
5. Influence over a person means keeping their hearts warm to you: seek the heart strings.
6. Influence over an organization of any kind means position, which could be a factor of Access, Affluence, wealth, or disposition (respect, reputation, capability, etc.)
7. Influence can be insured by maintaining Positional Advantage, which can be maintained with forward momentum *or* deft measurement of a person's or organization's tendency/propensity³.
8. Influence can also be insured by the *appearance* of gain or momentum. "Perception is reality."
9. Insurance premiums come with inflated price adjustments, and these should be 'shopped around'; so too one must change contacts to maintain a healthy Access which is at least fair if not sided with oneself.
10. Insurance is weighty, a literal cost, and a worry; it is another form of restraint on Influence. Fear limits exposure and risk, and that restrains Influence with more aggressive ventures, and Access to more influential partners.

³ Historical trends and analytics are the best measure of the propensity; but gut feeling is important as well.

G: Influencing Others Without Restraint

1. It is illegal to bribe or embezzle; and although those methods open some doors, they lead to the worst doors and loss of all Influence and Access.
2. Therefore when we speak of 'without restraint' it is meant that the Influence comes *of itself* rather than paying premiums or giving freemiums.
3. This comes only from the power of networks, from Awesomeness, and a desire of the warm-hearted and joyous participants which want to extend Influence - your Influence - for free.
4. Therefore the first step is warming hearts, the second step is maintaining hearts through contact and provision of favour, and the third step is expectation of return.
5. Return which is outwardly expected must be verbally explained and visibly provided; return which is secretly expected, or quietly agreed upon must never be verbally explained (or trust ends), and invisibly provided.
6. Once the "grass bends under the influence of the wind," expectations of a *ratio* of returns or profits must be cautiously-optimistically guarded, tracked, and utilized in gratitude.
7. If people feel appreciatingly used, and reciprocated, they will **keep themselves under Influence**. If they feel it is cleverly done to their disadvantage they will find a way to stop it up.
8. Touch one, then another, and move in this way in a spiral, warming hearts, and avoiding much closeness for "familiarity breeds contempt."
9. Ask for few favors in a short period of time, and large favors rarely; provide a bevy of small favors continuously, but never beg for the right of Influence or Access. It must be unstated as a matter of magnanimity.
10. Being bigger than others, emotionally, positionally, in affluence, or in generosity must be known to all without being trumpeted to all, therefore jealousy, avarice, capriciousness, and envy (stemming from greed).

H: The Power of Networks

1. A network is powered by the number of nodes, and the quality of connections.
2. Therefore the strength of the network is measured by two ways, averaged:
 - a. The number of nodes squared.
 - b. The maximal tension applicable to the weakest connection in the network.
3. Power has many equations influencing its calculation, but in this case we want a network to get things done, and to share currency, and reduce tension. So the network shares Load.
4. Load is not mere tension, but also weight and inertia - heft - upon the Network.
5. When a network snaps, the power snapback rule comes into place, and that means contagion can spread into Access and Influence networks; keys may break or locks may change: doors previously open become shut.
6. A strong network can help one Influence "without restraint" by carrying the load. Of course, this network will be limited to (according to cautious reasoning) the weakest nodal connection.
7. When a node (such as a partnership or friendship) crumbles, it must be expected to affect other nodes; if it is very toxic or negative, the effect may compound. Access and Influence can be lost.
8. However, a Network is like a fungus/mycelium, it needs merely be nourished with warmth and lubricated, and it will adapt and recover with time. Simply remove the source of poison and personally lift the Load off the Network.

9. As the Network recovers, its matrix needs strength testing to improve the scarification and test its resilience: give it work to do, but not a heavy load. Drop expectations.
10. When networks lift a Load, or spread it out, or transform it - whatever the capability of the Network is as it is designed - it will enrich Influence and Access, and extend one's Affluence. Therefore the wind is strong, but the forest is stronger than the wind or the grass⁴.

I: Flowering Influence

1. In the flowering process, there is blooming, there is a blossom/ing, and there is a fruiting.
2. When opportunities bloom, then Influence can spread, like a pollen; only it is from you in the center.
 - a. These influences are too any and small, you have to choose one blossom.
3. When a situation or relationship blossoms, the ability to influence a particular person, to warm them and hope to open a new doorway is at a budding, fragile place. It must be guarded.
4. When the blossom bears a fruit, there is a time period of potential ripening, where there is under-ripe, ripe, over-ripe, and rotten (toxic), plus a fruit can be taken by foxes and squirrels.
5. The fruits and flowers of Influence are of manifold types, and they *cross-pollinate* in weird, elaborate, and often unexpected ways.
6. A sweet fruit (opportunity) will be desired by all.
7. A sour fruit (shrivelling access or influence for a rival) will be enjoyed for the effect of creating increase via the shrinkage of the enemy.
8. A bitter fruit will mean loss for yourself or another: feed it to the other and enjoy Influence over their fate.
9. To Influence in a way that blooms opportunities - eager budding - takes a dedication to helping and influencing others positively.
10. The flowering of influence is related to opportunity, but also to the 'roots' of Access, and the water of wealth. Also, the flower should be grown in quality 'soil' meaning networks well tilled and tested.

J: Influencing the Affluent

1. The Affluent think and feel differently; same biology, different psychology and chemistry.
2. The Affluent have either huge or interesting egos, which must be respected; or hated.
3. The Affluent are also normal people when they are not being incredibly different.
4. Therefore to Influence the Affluent requires first to think like them.
5. Be incredibly selfish.
6. The Affluent are actually charitable, but selfishly so; however success enables them to do far more.
7. Affluency can come to small people, if they associate (have Access) to larger people.
8. Fame is a fickle dame, so don't try to woo her; let fame woo you.
9. Affluency requires increased expenses, and comfort with larger numbers, higher quality everything, and higher risk⁵, above all.
10. To attain and retain Affluency, learn to say "no" - and maybe to be a complete selfish asshole.
 - a. It requires a lot of focus and concentration to gather Affluence, and that requires eliminating distractions.
 - b. It also requires giving *your* distractions to other people. To loved ones, etc.

⁴ Grass equates to the individuals. The forest to organizations, but also to connected people with common purpose.

⁵ Don't forget that "risk can gut power quickly." (Axioms of Power)

K: Cashing in on Influence & Affluence

1. Cashing in on Influence is most like sex: it's dirty but good, and the dirtier (while legal), probably the better. You should feel naughty, and get used to that naughty feeling.
2. Be the "Big Swinging Dick."
3. Affluence oozes, Influence pressures.
4. Affluency in a given area is more easy to transfer to another area than Influence, so long as there is Access.
5. But if you are "out of region," and borrowing that Access, you will need **permission** to use someone else's Influence
6. It's easier to beg for forgiveness than ask for permission...
7. So therefore skip the asking permission and presume upon your Influence (weak as it may be) with that person, and measure the risk to "burning a bridge."
 - a. It all depends on the closeness to the Accessory; see Guiguzi
8. "Get out while the gettin's good."
 - a. "Get in. Get it done. Get it done **right**. Get out."
9. Once you cash in, avoid bragging for 2 weeks to 3 months, depending on how dirty the ~~sex...~~ transaction.
10. Convert some (unless you are retiring and don't care who knows!) of it back into Access and Influence insurance, and maintain your Affluence; ideally you should have compounded your Affluence at a 2:1 or 3:1 ratio for the Influence or Access.
 - a. **Beware:** affluence wanes faster, like a new car's value. Once you drive off the lot, it drops fast. Therefore the wise cash out influence and affluence for **more Influence** and a 'hard asset' of Access.
 - b. Do not give up Access willingly⁶.

L: The Affluency Analogies

1. Being Affluent does not mean you perform The Fuck on every person or deal; it just means you can fuck em or tell them to fuck off, or get fucked, and there really isn't any major repercussion; but there are **always consequences**.
2. Being Affluent means never having to buy subsistence for/from yourself. It's living "Hand to pocket." But it isn't always clear whose pocket your hand is in and whose hand is in *your* pocket. So check on that, from time to time.
3. Being Affluent is the round robin of circle-jerks. As long as everyone has a good time, it really isn't a big deal. But you just know someone is having less fun getting fucked than everyone else. That person either wants Access or has no Influence.
4. You can fuck someone out of Influence, but only they can fuck themselves out of Affluence.⁷
 - a. Neglect of their network is part of that process.

⁶ When I quit the NSA and gave up my Top Secret clearance, my master's disciple, another 5th or 6th degree, chastised me and told me I shouldn't have quit. On the one hand he was worried for my future. But on a subconscious level they all wanted my Access - the 'masters' I mean. Ironically, as I rose in Position and Affluence in the school, various people felt threatened by my unprecedented Access there, and schemed to eliminate it.

⁷ The story of EZ E (the rapper) is one of the classic examples of both.

5. Affluenza is when you catch a rare case of “can’t touch this” in the exact opposite of how MC Hammer meant it... and then all Access and Influence will be lost like you have leprosy or the Plague. In fact it’d be better if you did.
6. Affluent people have problems, big problems, which often require big solutions. But sometimes the solutions are so tiny and minor, they can’t see them though it’s right there, or easy. Hence a lot of lost careers and suicides in Hollywood and sports.
7. Affluency lost is the biggest joy for people without any, and you can expect a bandwagon of hate. Everyone will want to run train on the failure, whereas before they were lining up to suck the Big Swinging Dick.
8. Therefore “keep your friends close, and keep your enemies closer” *but also* “with friends like these, who needs enemies?” So it is said that the Affluent keep distance with everyone and trust relatively few people.
9. Affluence is less important than Access, but it isn’t exactly separate. So if you can be an *Accessory* to the Affluent, you can benefit, and generally avoid the taint of their failures. But beware the Jafar effect.
10. Affluenza is worse than influenza, but Influenza is the worst. It will have you bleeding out the ass and nose, and crying tears of blood as you see those you had Influence over before gather in spades to crush you and exact their “pound of flesh” on the way out.

M: Affluence and Access

1. The biggest mistake of those with Affluence is that they try to get more Influence. But this is like using sugar to slake your thirst. Affluence uses up Influence as a rule.
2. Therefore the proper way to use Affluence is to open doors and get **as much Access as possible**.
3. With Access you can then combine a lower and secure access with Affluency, *and purchase Influence*.
4. The axis of Affluence :: Access is most hinged upon becoming an *Accessory*. That doesn’t mean you have to be a lapdog, or footstool/rest.
5. Affluence purchased by selling Access is short lived, and less appreciated than Access purchased with Affluence; this means if you sell off your Access, don’t expect much in return except gratitude, and if you buy Access with your fame and affluence, it’s customary to not return the favor.
 - a. This is because Access is worth more Value.
6. Therefore if you sell Access it must be for Influence, but if you purchase Access, it should yield both Influence and enhance your Affluence.
7. Affluence sold for Access is quite a deal; anyone who thinks they can purchase fame and Affluence directly is a chump worthy of scamming.
8. Selling Influence for Access is often illegal, but selling it for Affluence (a trade, often in sex as a medium) is probably a fair deal, though usually foolish.
9. Affluence :: Access is mitigated by the opportunity changes.
10. Access doors sometimes - but very rarely - have fame and fortune behind them. Don’t be afraid to open as many doors with as many keys as possible. But don’t seek Affluence this way, let it come slowly.

N: Awesomeness

1. Systems which are given the conditions to build, to enrich and enrich, enrichen and enrichen, by their enrichening reach a crescendo of unstoppable Positional Advantage. This is termed Awesomeness.

2. In Influential terms, Awesomeness comes not merely from unstoppable Shi and Actual, or even Raw Power and Political Power, it is a “wind that blows all day.” It goes *everywhere*.
3. “Even a strong wind does not blow all day.” This is the warning that Awesomeness comes to an end.
4. When an arrow reaches its end of trajectory, it is important to not be on the arrow for the crash down; so cash out when the turbulence increases to that point.
5. As for the use of Awesomeness, it is unwieldy. It tends to inflate and inflate, decreasing its power and ability/concentration.
6. So use it sparingly in Influence, and avoid as much as possible its use in Affluence; focus instead on concentrated power plays in small positions to unlock more and more Access to create more Position and move *cautiously forward*.
7. Awesomeness is like a nuclear bomb, or a tornado, or an avalanche - it is a force of nature, a result of the crescendo of raw power. Therefore what is gained over a long period is lost sometimes in a single day⁸.
8. Awesome Affluence usually looks to those without it like pomp and ceremony; but to the elite with unending Influence, it looks like full Access, and the ability to crush or smash-n-grab at will.
9. Awesomeness is pierced by potency, such as sharp Killing Qi, or much raw or destructive power; but if it is aware of the threat, beware Just or War or Evil Power’s revenge.
10. Awesome Power and Awesome Affluence are one and the same: both depend on Access and Influence.

O: Power and Affluence

1. Power is a measure of the raw energy, in work over time, or in currency multiplied by tension, which yields the source of how Affluence and Influence impact upon the system.
2. If the system is human, such as society, or politics, then power will include the ability to create Sway.
3. Sway is not mere wooing; nor is it gravitas. Sway is an energetic pressuring, which is often proportional to the magnanimity of the leader.
4. In this way, gravitas is related to the Sway, because gravitas shows the heft of the leader, and magnanimity is the show of this position and gravitas.
5. Therefore the leader who wants Influence and Affluence gathers first the “love of the People [men]” and then maintains its access no matter what⁹.
6. Sway follows the rules of power, and the rules of affluence, et al. However, it is itself a child, a new product of them, and has its own rules.
7. In brief, Sway is not gathered, but always in motion.
8. The attainment of the “Royal Sway” or ‘hegemony’ is the end goal of all the Awesomeness, Love of the Men, and Pinnacle Position (PP).
9. The Royal Sway is the most jealously coveted position at all times.
10. It is the prerogative of the Sage to guard the Royal Sway, or else darkness ascends the throne.

⁸ Although not in a single day there are two good examples; one is the Influential martial power of General Donald Rumsfeld, who gained power over decades and came to the top of the neocon wave during the 9/11 and post years’ War on Terror. But the failure to find WMDs in 2005 ended that power. Another is an antique reference. After the overthrow on Dong Guo through a long played, clever ruse in the era just after the Yellow Turban rebellion, the Prime Minister of the Han tried to run the empire, and underestimate a minor alliance. This turned out to be a major blunder and the ally became an enemy and invaded. Within a very short period the empire fell, and Cao Cao eventually captured the emperor. The Han never rose to prominence again.

⁹ The rumor is that Alexander the Great’s own men turned on him and murdered him. They were willing to cross Asia, but eventually they’d had enough. The Influence ended, when the Access to their hearts did, as they cooled of love and raged with hate.

P Strategies of the Affluent, and of the Sage

1. The Game of Thrones is ancient, and it is the pinnacle game of Affluence.
2. The Sage therefore considers it very important to monitor (and traditionally not to try to ascend) the throne while playing the Game of Thrones.
3. In the strategies of the Affluent, there is bingfa (martial strategy) and zongheng (rhetoric & alliances), which are used to leverage Influence and planning across distances.
4. Therefore the wise have always sought Access to wisdom and information first.
5. In the modern age, Access to information has never been greater, and therefore, the mass of affluency has never been more spread out.
6. Dilution is the first obstacle to overcome, therefore concentration is the first strategy.
7. Concentration on strategy comes before a focus on the structure.
8. The Sage therefore considers the formless before the form.
9. As for the Affluent, the unwise, and most famous who follow their egos, they consider form first, and therefore lose the Essential, and lose the Central, and lose the handle of all these forces.
10. It is essential, therefore, that the wise consider the use of currency, as a form of energetic flux, to moderate the formed and formless mediums which affect Affluency, etc.

Q: Affluent Currency

1. A current is a stream of something; in the case of money it is a stream of units of finance. But ideas have currency as well, meaning in the present, but also in trade.
2. Money is not all that has hold over the hearts of people and enables Access and Influence.
3. Therefore the most important currency is not what people have, or don't have, but what they want.
4. The wise restrain the display of their wants outwardly, and keep totally hidden their innermost desires.
5. So there is another currency which is of use: the currency of potential.
6. Potential is not as concrete as a promise, and so it is difficult to hold anyone to anything upon Potential.
7. Nevertheless Potential Affluency, etc. leads many to be easily Influenced.
8. As "perception equals reality," by dangling Potential (but not Promises) in front of people, you may attain Sway over them.
9. This, in general can lead to Affluency, but it will be difficult without sacrifice and surrender.
10. Current is tension over resistance (impedance), or a difference of induction; so we must know that inducing people, events, situations, nations, policies, politics, etc. is the height of Affluency.

R: Tension, Intention, Attention, and Power

1. Tension, whether it is intention or attention, is a measure of currency and resistance; but Power is tension coupled with currency.
2. Potential Power (PP) is its own currency.
3. Hold attention to a goal, such as gaining Access, and PP will convert into Real Power (RP).
4. Currency in motion, is how to induce Influence, but various means of conversion exist which can *synthesize* Influence and Affluence.

5. In terms of conversion, Access enables leverage and the ability to apply torque to any situation, in order to force a conversion or yielding of results.
6. But the best *forceful* device (or artifice) is technology.
7. Techno-Access is nearly as good as PP through *real life* Access (or paper Access).
8. However, its unreliability makes technology dangerous as an anchor or foundation.
9. Therefore, rely upon traditional forms of Power, and those rules, and make your attention and intention like one power - like a thunderclap which accompanies the lightning - and reduce the tension that impedes the current and flow of Power.
10. Keep attention and intention within the bounds acceptable by rules, by Destiny, by Heaven's Will, by social conventions of propriety, and then one may retain PP, RP, Sway, Position, and Access, and - Lord Willing - Awesomeness.

S: Maintaining the Triad

1. The reader should, by now, note the importance of maintenance of the difficult to retain Triad of Access, Influence, and Affluence - another name in general will be the Assets.
2. To maintain the Assets one must first appreciate them.
3. To appreciate them you must appreciate *not having them*.
4. The pain of lack of Access and the sting to the pride for lack of Influence, and the frustration at unfairness when others have Affluence that you do not will guide one to desire the Assets, Sway, Position, PP, etc.
5. The Triad, however, is naturally mutually circular and nourishing. It obeys the Triquetra¹⁰.
6. The 'three powers' of the Triad also control each other, as has been described.
7. Therefore you use them to maintain each other.
8. But all the Assets require *Currency*, and usually that means money and monetary power, but not always.
9. It is most important to consider maintenance and foresight of future needs, as a priority over acquisition of *new* Assets.
10. The biggest mistake that can be made is not valuing the smallest, seemingly most insignificant Asset, and moving too quickly onto new ones, and losing both.

T: Buying and Selling the Triad

1. Just as one may want to "cash in" on Affluence, one will eventually want to "cash out" on the Triad of PP and RP, and all the Sway which *cannot* be sold (nor can Awesomeness). But as with everything, timing is key.
2. Most try to cash out after the value is already dropping. One's "Star" is crestfallen, and therefore, how can one expect anything to be as it should?
3. To get *what you deserve*, and not merely what you have earned, you need to take graceful exits at the appropriate time.
4. Graceful does not mean weak, or to just take the first offer that comes along.
5. If you've been in too long and had no offers, then you have to take your first offers.

¹⁰ The circle represents the Power or *motion of Energy*.

6. When it comes to cashing out of non-transferrable positions, like Tenure, a license, fame, etc. you need to understand you are cashing out for a *Legacy*.
7. A Legacy will have some of the Influence (pennies on the dollar worth) and some fame or Affluence, but hopefully more peace.
8. Selling will be best if you want out fast to go to the bigger competitor; but if you want the best price find the hungry up-and-comer who will give you the value you think you deserve. Don't be afraid to self-finance and take a promise note from the buyer of your Assets.
9. If they are not hard Assets but more soft, like "who you know" the trick is to 'sell' to a Protege and keep your Influence over him or her.
10. To measure up the Protege, measure up by the Legacy you built/want to build, and what they want to build.

U: Owning and Protecting Resources

1. Proteges are one type of resource that goes along with having a Legacy of Assets. Along the way there are many kinds:
 - a. Reputation
 - b. Brand
 - c. Advisors and trusted counselors
 - d. Liaisons
 - e. Connections or bridges (mezzanine)
 - f. Capital - both money and goodwill
 - g. Knowledge and research
 - h. Accessories
2. Aside from "insuring" your Influence, and trying to maintain your Sway and increase your PP and Position, there are other ways to protect these resources:
 - a. Security
 - b. Cybersecurity
 - c. "Shoring" up relationships
 - d. Greasing palms aka "buying votes"
 - e. "Banking" on someone or something which puts you far ahead of the pack.
 - f. "Next Level" development
3. When you own anything, aside from ordinary maintenance (like an oil change would be), there is extraordinary maintenance (like taking a vehicle to the dealer for a tuneup on specified mileages), which often requires a *Protection Plan*.
4. Therefore, makes plans for the protection of your Assets and resources, as you would for a car or home.
5. But also consider enriching your Assets, as indicative of the freedom of movement you really want to have.
6. If you can enrich and enrich your allies, and harness new levels of Access thereby, then you are sadi to have the right Sway, whether or not it is the Royal Sway.¹¹
7. It may also be advisable, in some instances to form partnerships with others who want the Sway, or to share it, and to give them a role in your dreams and use of the Assets.

¹¹ In the fictional works, Sherlock Holmes is able to solve problems for royal families, even kings, throughout his distinguished private career, until no one in the world of crime and justice is more famous than he is. His reputation precedes him. This is what I mean by the Right Sway. It befits his sagely status.

8. This can be a dangerous proposition so be careful with whom you share this privilege.
9. Remember that Affluenza is contagious so investigate your potential partners and double check upon their own resources and reputations as well¹².
10. When you own a resource, do not abuse the ownership or you just may lose that resource.

V: Extending Power through Leverage Using Your Network

1. When you have Power you will want more of it.
2. This is called extension and it gives advantage at a distance.
3. Advantage at a distance is called leverage, and it results in the ability to apply pressure at the end of a power delivery device.
4. This is termed “torque” and it can help one convert a soft asset like your Network into something “hard.”
5. A Network may be as maximally weak as its weakest node, but it is also as minimally powerful as its most powerful node.
6. Therefore form a close bond with that asset, and gain Access and Influence over this person or thing.
7. Then use it, not too much, as thou willest.
8. Grasp Access and Influence with both grasping clutches of hands, and never let it go, willingly - until you cash out.
9. Dangle this grasp in front of members of your Network and treat them to a bit of ‘carrot and stick’ action.
10. Reward your Network (yin) with your “Big Swinging Dick” (yang), and splodge them with the “cum” (life giving force) that comes from wild, egregious use of Influence from time to time. Excite them. Be appropriate for the venue, the sexual metaphor is a visual, not a literal.

W: Winning Position

1. Life is a competition; so practice daily.
2. Win Position anyway you can, within appropriate legal, ethical, and moral boundaries.
3. Don’t cede Positional Advantage away to anyone, not even a spouse, not even during sex.
4. Even when you are down, people should think you’re “on top of things.”
5. When some risk rips a big hole in your Assets, in your Triad etc., pretend they have not outwardly, and then work like mad privately to sew up the hole. Then it **never happened** as far as you or anyone’s concerned.
6. Take risks, earn rewards, capitalize on gains.
7. Learn to retreat gracefully, and to mitigate defeat.
8. Open new positions as seeds for the future, and don’t presume on past successes.
9. Flex your position, sometimes for no reason at all, just because you can.
10. Take new positions and try new things; these seeds on rare occasions lead to bigger and better things.

¹² The Universe or God will rearrange the right people into place for you, if you meet up with them in time; but sometimes things get in your way and they can misinterpret and you lose that new partner or resource. In such a case it is custom to say “it wasn’t meant to be” as opposed to having ‘sour grapes.’ That doesn’t make it 100% right, for sometimes there are truly lamentable missed opportunities. However, it is probably healthier.

X: Reputation and Sway

1. Reputation precedes you.
2. It is hard to come by, and nowadays even harder to protect.
3. Sway follows you.
4. It is even harder to come by and is fickle and easily lost... being a reified substance.
5. Therefore take measures to use your Sway with people and on the Internets to maintain your Reputation, especially of honesty, health, mental balance, reliability, and courage.
6. As for the Sway, protect it by using it the **right amount**, not too much nor too little.
7. This may mean swallowing your pride sometimes, or postponing revenge, or avoiding abusing someone or some power when you otherwise might/could.
8. Reputation Management is now a major online resource/service; but there is **no one** to protect your Sway; it is up to you!
9. Sway Management is not merely about timid use, it is about lots of tiny tests given to your Network, to probe and find weaknesses and test loyalties.
10. If you fail to test your Network, when it fails you, you'll have no one else to blame, and yet it may be the end of your career! How unfortunate that would be!

Y: Converting Gains into Intangibles

1. Of course it is *typical* to speak of the conversion of the Assets into tangibles/fungibles such as cash, options, bonds, shares, real estate, etc.
2. But what most would like to know is about the *perks*... and this is absolutely what one should ask about, because life is not about money.
 - a. "It's good to be king..."
3. The most important conversion should be into the *pursuit of happiness*, through seeking means and situations which create happiness for self and others; do not buy happiness, it cannot be bought.
4. Instead, ask oneself *who* can give one Access to *opportunities* to do charitable goodness, philanthropic works, spiritual works, and other happiness generating opportunities.
5. Use Affluence to get to know worthy people.
6. Use Influence to sway others and woo them *to your side*; to be **worthy**, and to bring balance to some System which one cares about.
7. One of the best intangibles (besides Legacy) is Satisfaction or "Lifetime Achievement" - usually measured in awards, accolades, plaques, statues, etc. but if wealthy enough names on libraries, roads, bridges, colleges, etc.
8. Another type of intangible benefit is *free time* to exercise *free will*. It is usual for retirees to complain of a lack of free time: this merely indicates a failure to "cash out" on [capital] gains into the more important, intangible things in life, for the *Artha* stage of life.
9. Therefore as a person enters the final stages of life, they should remove the attachments of kama (householder life), and seek a more *spiritual* result.
10. Intangible benefits are what Assets should be about, not mere Power. Thus can a man or woman say they have truly lives.

Z: Living with Affluence

1. To be Affluent is actually to be either:
 - a. Alone on a pinnacle, dominant, a Rock for others
 - b. Or connected to everything, and everyone.
 - c. The difference is if one cares or not.
2. Affluency is potentially a blessing/fortune or a curse/misfortune... it all depends on how you view and use the Assets.
3. All creations of mankind are *tools* - implements for improvement - and meant to be **used**. So are various other creations not made by mankind ... and we will leave it at that.
4. As you become more powerful with greater Assets, it's vital to know who and what to use, when, why (as well as how), to avoid becoming small in mind and heart, used and abused by others, and how to defend oneself from all sorts of characters and attackers.
5. One must consider the danger presented by the presence of Access and the other Assets discussed.
6. Consider the use, therefore, of security, greater space, added bodyguards, protections, etc. if one is unable to be completely anonymous in this Affluence.
7. Not all Affluence is public or well known. Or under threat¹³.
8. What is a Life? Life is a vibration and a purpose, a movement towards something. But think of living with Affluence as Life+ ; which would make living without these Assets Life- (minus).
9. Living with an **Affluent Purpose** should be the goal of any sage, ruler, sage-ruler, executive, commander, religious teacher, or leader of any type, because they should desire the Sway to influence the world towards the (hopefully positive) goal they desire.
10. If one has the Spiritual Power, this then becomes part of the *magick* of combining the formed and formless, known and unknown, in order to bring Access to its final level in Artha: access to the next level of reality (in the afterlife).

¹³ Sam Walton and Warren Buffet were known to frequent the public for ice cream, shopping, etc. without any type of bodyguard protection.